

Seaweed polysaccharides as macromolecular crowding agents

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ABSTRACT

Development of mesenchymal stem cell-based tissue engineered implantable devices requires prolonged in vitro culture for the development of a three-dimensional implantable device, which leads to phenotypic drift, thus hindering the clinical translation and commercialisation of such approaches. Macromolecular crowding, a biophysical phenomenon based on the principles of excluded-volume effect, dramatically accelerates and increases extracellular matrix deposition during in vitro culture. However, the optimal macromolecular crowder is still elusive. Herein, we evaluated the biophysical properties of various concentrations of different seaweed in origin sulphated polysaccharides and their effect on human adipose derived stem cell cultures. Carrageenan, possibly due to its high sulphation degree, exhibited the highest negative charge values. No correlation was observed between the different concentrations of the crowders and charge, polydispersity index, hydrodynamic radius and fraction volume occupancy across all crowders. None of the crowders, but arabinogalactan, negatively affected cell viability. Carrageenan, fucoidan, galactofucan and ulvan increased extracellular matrix (especially collagen type I and collagen type V) deposition. Carrageenan induced the highest osteogenic effect and galactofucan and fucoidan demonstrated the highest chondrogenic effect. All crowders were relatively ineffective with respect to adipogenesis. Our data highlight the potential of sulphated seaweed polysaccharides for tissue engineering purposes.

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1. Introduction

Mesenchymal stem cell (MSC) therapies have shown immense potential as therapeutic strategies for regeneration and repair of injured or diseased organs and tissues [1,2]. Considering that direct cell injections are characterised by poor cell survival and localisation at the implantation site [3,4] and recent data advocating the beneficial effects MSCs' secretome [5–7], research efforts are directed towards methods that enhance extracellular matrix (ECM) synthesis and deposition. Indeed, the intertwined ECM not only protects the implanted cells, but also acts as a factory of therapeutic, angiogenic, immunomodulating and anticancer factors [8,9]. To this end, cell, and in particular MSC, sheet engineering has achieved significant strides. For example, a phase I clinical trial, utilising autologous skeletal-muscle derived stem cell sheets, demonstrated functional recovery of patients with severe heart failure [10]. Another study showed that allogenic human adipose-derived stem cell (hADSC) sheets promoted functional wound healing in patients with non-ischemic diabetic foot ulcers [11]. Despite these promising even in clinical setting data, only a handful of cell-sheet products have been commercialised (e.g. Apligraf®,

Organogenesis Inc., bovine collagen matrix seeded with neonatal foreskin fibroblasts and keratinocytes; Dermagraft®, Advanced BioHealing Inc., bioabsorbable polygalactin mesh seeded with neonatal fibroblasts) and none of them exploits the MSCs' secretome. This limited technology transfer from benchtop to clinic has been attributed to the prolonged in vitro culture time required to develop an implantable device that is associated with cell phenotypic drift and senescence [12,13] and extremely high manufacturing costs [14,15].

Macromolecular crowding (MMC) is a biophysics-oriented technique that involves the addition of macromolecules to reaction or culture media. Following the principles of excluded volume effect (two molecules cannot occupy the same space at the same time), MMC significantly increases rates and kinetics of biochemical reactions and biological processes [16,17]. For example, MMC has been extensively utilised to study polymer looping dynamic properties [18–20]; DNA structure [21–23], condensation [24,25], replication [26,27] and stability [28–30]; and RNA and protein transcription [31,32], structure [33,34] and folding/unfolding kinetics and equilibria [35–42]. In eukaryotic cell culture, recent research endeavours have utilised MMC to enhance and accelerate ECM deposition (Fig. 1). In standard dilute cell culture, the enzymatic conversion of water-soluble procollagen to insoluble collagen is extremely slow [43–45]. MMC, by imitating the dense and crowded native tissue milieu, restrains/prohibits the diffusion of

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Fig. 1. Macromolecular crowding, in eukaryotic cell culture, remarkably accelerates and enhances extracellular matrix deposition.

procollagen and *N*- and *C*- proteinases in the culture media, resulting in an over 80-fold increase in collagen (and associated ECM) deposition within 48 h of culture [46].

In the quest of the ideal, with respect to rate, quality and quantity of deposited ECM, various crowders have been assessed with variable results to-date. A Ficoll™ 70 kDa and Ficoll™ 400 kDa cocktail has been shown to induce supramolecular assembly and alignment of deposited ECM in human bone marrow MSC (hBMSC) cultures [47] and to increase osteogenic and adipogenic differentiation of hADSCs [48]. In addition, the Ficoll™ cocktail has been shown to facilitate brown adipocyte differentiation in hBMSC cultures, as evidenced by substantially upregulating uncoupling protein 1 and uncoupled respiration [49]. Polyvinylpyrrolidone 360 kDa has been shown to increase cell proliferation and ECM deposition in hBMSC cultures [50]. Dextran sulphate 500 kDa has been shown to enhance collagen type I and fibronectin deposition and to increase adipogenic and osteogenic differentiation of hBMSC cultures [51]. A cocktail of dextran sulphate 10 kDa, Ficoll™ 70 and Ficoll™ 70 400 was utilised to produce highly organised decellularised extracellular matrices from hBMSCs, capable of retaining glycosaminoglycans and growth factors and, as a result, supporting human hematopoietic stem and progenitor cells expansion [52].

Among the various crowding molecules that have been assessed, carrageenan has been shown to induce the highest ECM deposition in the shortest period of time, largely attributed to its negative charge and high polydispersity that collectively result in more efficient volume exclusion [46,53]. In hBMSC cultures, carrageenan has been shown to enhance native ECM deposition [53] and to induce chondrogenic and osteogenic differentiation [54,55], due to its sulphated nature. Indeed, sulphated polysaccharides have been shown to induce chondrogenic differentiation via inhibition of alkaline phosphatase and osteopontin expression [56–64]; to induce osteogenic differentiation via enhanced BMP-2 activity and via the phosphoinositide 3-kinase/Akt/RUNX2 pathway [65–67]; and to inhibit adipogenesis via the mitogen-activated protein kinase pathway [68], via inhibition of insulin signalling [69–71] and via interaction with FGF-2 [72–74]. Although carrageenan is extensively used in pharma and food industries, its association, albeit questionable [75], with colitis, may restrict its use in regenerative medicine, imposing the need to identify alternative crowders. It is worth noting that recent data indicate that the carrageenan-induced colitis is related to changes to host intestinal microecology, as opposed to a direct effect of the molecule [76,77].

Seaweeds are a rich source of sulphated polysaccharides (e.g. carrageenan, fucoidan, fucan, galactan, ulvan) with interesting, for tissue engineering, chemical and biological properties (e.g. anticoagulant,

antiinflammatory, antioxidant antitumor, antiviral) [78–80]. Although the effect of seaweed-derived polysaccharides on stem cell differentiation has been well-established (e.g. fucoidan has been shown to induce osteogenic and chondrogenic differentiation of hBMSCs [81,82], sulphated polysaccharide extracted from the green seaweed *Caulerpa* increased osteogenic differentiation of hMSCs isolated from Wharton jelly [83]), their potential as MMC agents is still unknown. Thus, herein, we ventured to assess the influence of fucoidan, galactofucan, arabinogalactan and ulvan in ECM deposition and stem cell lineage commitment.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Carrageenan (550 kDa) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Ireland) and fucoidan (600 kDa), galactofucan (700 kDa), arabinogalactan (140 kDa) and ulvan (300 kDa) were purchased from Elicityl (France) (Supplementary Table S1 provides their properties). Tissue culture consumables were purchased from Sarstedt (Ireland) and NUNC (Denmark). All other chemicals, cell culture media and reagents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Ireland), unless otherwise stated.

2.2. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements

Zeta potential, polydispersity index (PDI) and hydrodynamic radius of carrageenan (50 µg/ml) and different concentrations (25, 50, 100, 250 and 500 µg/ml) of fucoidan, galactofucan, arabinogalactan, and ulvan were assessed using dynamic light scattering (Zetasizer ZS90, Malvern Instruments, UK). The crowding solutions were prepared in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) to mimic physiological conditions. Fractional volume occupancy (FVO) was calculated using the obtained values of hydrodynamic radius for the different crowders, as has been described before [84].

2.3. Cell culture

Cells (hADSCs, RoosterBio, USA) were cultured in alpha-Minimum Essential Medium (αMEM) with GlutaMAX™ (Gibco Life Technologies, Ireland), supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1% penicillin streptomycin (P/S) at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂. Cells were used between passage 3 and 5. For MMC experiments, cells were seeded at 25,000 cells/cm² density and were allowed to attach for 24 h. Subsequently, the media were changed with media containing

100 μM of L-ascorbic acid 2-phosphate sesquimagnesium salt hydrate, to induce collagen synthesis, and the various concentrations of fucoidan, galactofucan, arabinogalactan and ulvan. Normal media (- MMC) and carrageenan (50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) were used as controls. Media were changed every 3 days.

2.4. Phase contrast microscopy

To evaluate the influence of different MMC conditions on cell morphology, an inverted microscope (Leica Microsystem, Germany) was used. Phase contrast images were captured at different timepoints (4, 7, 10 days) and were processed using ImageJ software (NIH, USA).

2.5. Cell viability

At the various timepoints (4, 7 and 10 days), calcein AM (Thermo Fisher Scientific, UK) and ethidium homodimer I (Thermo Fisher Scientific, UK) stainings were performed, as per manufacturer's protocol, to assess the influence of the different crowders on cell viability. Briefly, cells were washed with Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) and a solution of calcein AM (4 μM) and ethidium homodimer I (2 μM) were added. Cells were incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO_2 for 30 min after which, fluorescence images were captured with an Olympus IX-81 inverted fluorescence microscope (Olympus Corporation, Japan).

2.6. Cell proliferation analysis

At the various timepoints (4, 7 and 10 days) cells were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) and stained with Hoechst Fluorescent Stain (Thermo Fisher Scientific, UK) to stain nuclei. Fluorescent images were captured using an Operetta high content imaging system (PerkinElmer, USA) at 20 \times magnification. To assess cell number, three wells were imaged, three fields-of-view (FOV) were taken from each well (total of 9 images analysed per experimental group) and the images were analysed automatically using Harmony software version 3.0 (PerkinElmer, USA).

2.7. Cell metabolic activity

At the different timepoints (4, 7 and 10 days), the alamarBlue® assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific, UK) was used to evaluate the influence of MMC on cell metabolic activity, as per manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, at each time point, cells were washed with PBS and a 10% alamarBlue® solution in PBS was added to the cells. Cells were incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO_2 for 4 h and absorbance was measured at 550 nm and 595 nm with a Varioskan Flash Spectral scanning multi-mode reader (Thermo Fisher Scientific, UK). Cell metabolic activity was expressed as percentage reduction of the alamarBlue® dye and was first normalised to cell number and then normalised to the non-crowded control (- MMC).

2.8. Sodium dodecyl sulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDSPAGE)

SDS-PAGE was conducted as has been described previously [85]. Briefly, at the various timepoints (4, 7 and 10 days), culture media were aspirated and cell layers were briefly washed with HBSS. Cell layers were then digested with pepsin from porcine gastric mucosa at 0.1 mg/ml in 0.5 M acetic acid (Fischer Scientific, Ireland) at 37 °C for 2 h under agitation. Cell layers were then scraped and neutralised with 1 N sodium hydroxide. Cell layer samples were analysed by SDS-PAGE under non-reducing conditions using a Mini-Protean 3 system (Bio-Rad Laboratories, UK). Bovine collagen type I (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, Symatase Biomateriaux, France) was used as standard for all gels. Staining of the protein bands was performed with SilverQuest™ kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, UK) following manufacturer's instructions. To quantify the

cell-produced collagen type I deposition, the relative densities of collagen $\alpha 1(\text{I})$ and $\alpha 2(\text{I})$ chains were evaluated with ImageJ and compared to the $\alpha 1(\text{I})$ and $\alpha 2(\text{I})$ chain bands densities of standard collagen type I. After the quantification, results were normalised to the cell number.

2.9. Immunocytochemistry

At each timepoint (4, 7 and 10 days), cells were briefly washed with PBS and fixed with 4% PFA for 20 min at room temperature. Cell were washed again and non-specific site interactions were blocked with 3% bovine serum albumin (BSA) in PBS for 30 min. Cells were incubated overnight at 4 °C with the various primary antibodies (rabbit anti-collagen type I (Bio-Techne, UK), rabbit anti-collagen type III, rabbit anti-collagen V and rabbit anti-fibronectin (Abcam, UK), after which, they were washed 3 times with PBS, followed by 30 min incubation at room temperature with the secondary antibody (AlexaFluor® 488 goat anti rabbit, Thermo Fisher Scientific, UK). Nuclei were counter-stained with Hoechst Fluorescent Stain. Fluorescent images were captured with an Operetta high content imaging system (PerkinElmer, USA) at 20 \times magnification and relative fluorescent intensity was analysed automatically using Harmony software version 3.0 (PerkinElmer, USA). Three replicates per conditions were imaged and three FOV were taken from each well (total of 9 images analysed per experimental group). Relative fluorescent intensity was normalised to the cell number.

2.10. Tri-lineage differentiation assay

For all differentiation experiments cells at passage 5 were seeded at a density of 25,000 cells/cm². Osteogenic, adipogenic and chondrogenic assays were performed either without (-) or with (+) MMC preconditioning prior to differentiation, and without (-) or with (+) MMC in the differentiation media. The MMC treatments used were 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ carrageenan, 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ fucoidan, 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ galactofucan and 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ulvan. For non-preconditioned cells, osteogenic, adipogenic and chondrogenic differentiations were initiated 24 h after seeding and cells were differentiated for 21 days. For preconditioned cells, MMC media were added 24 h after seeding. After 4 days of MMC, media were switched to osteogenic, adipogenic or chondrogenic media, respectively, and cells were differentiated for 21 days.

Osteogenesis was induced using medium composed of α MEM with GlutaMAX™ supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% P/S, 50 μM L-ascorbic acid 2-phosphate sesquimagnesium salt hydrate, 10 mM β -glycerophosphate, 100 μM dexamethasone, without and with MMC. Adipogenesis was induced through cycles by 7 days of induction media composed of Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium high glucose (DMEM-HG), supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% P/S, 1 μM Rosiglitazone, 1 μM dexamethasone, 0.5 mM 3-isobutyl-1-methylxanthine, 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ insulin, without and with MMC and subsequently with maintenance media, composed of DMEM-HG, supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% P/S and 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ insulin, without and with MMC, respectively. For chondrogenic differentiation 250,000 cells were dispensed to round bottom wells of 96-well plates. Differentiation was induced using media composed of DMEM-HG, supplemented with 10 ng/ml transforming growth factor $\beta 3$ (TGF- $\beta 3$, PromoCell, Germany), 100 nM dexamethasone, 10% insulin-transferrin-selenium, 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ L-proline, 100 μM L-ascorbic acid 2-phosphate sesquimagnesium salt hydrate, without and with MMC.

2.11. Alizarin red staining and quantification of uptake

After 21 days of osteogenic differentiation, phase contrast images were captured. Subsequently, cells were fixed with ice-cold methanol for 20 min, stained with 2% alizarin red in deionised water for 15 min and washed with deionised water. Images were acquired using an inverted microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany). Semi-

quantitative analysis of alizarin red staining was performed by dissolving the bound stain with 10% acetic acid. Samples were collected using a cell scraper and heated to 85 °C for 10 min. Subsequently 10% solution of ammonium hydroxide was used to achieve a pH of 4.5. Finally, the absorbance was read at 405 nm using a micro-plate reader (Varioskan Flash, Thermo Scientific, Ireland). Results were normalised to DNA quantity.

2.12. Oil red O staining and quantification of uptake

After 21 days of adipogenic differentiation, phase contrast images were captured. Subsequently, cells were fixed for 20 min with 4% PFA, stained for 15 min with oil red O solution (oil red O 0.5% in isopropanol, diluted 3:2 in distilled water) at room temperature and images were acquired using an inverted microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany). For quantification of oil red O staining, the dye was extracted pipetting 100% isopropanol over the surface of the wells. Then, the solution was centrifuged at 500g for 2 min to remove debris and the absorbance was measured at 520 nm using a Varioskan Flash plate reader (ThermoFisher Scientific). Results were normalised to DNA quantity.

2.13. Glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) and DNA quantification

Cell layers and culture media were digested for 3 h at 60 °C with 0.1% crystallised papain in 0.2 M sodium phosphate buffer pH 6.4, containing sodium acetate, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, disodium salt and cysteine-HCl. For GAG quantification, a Blyscan™ Glycosaminoglycan Assay (Biocolor, Carrickfergus, UK) was used. Results were normalised to DNA quantity.

2.14. DNA quantification

DNA quantification was assessed using the Quant-iT™ PicoGreen® dSDNA assay kit (Invitrogen, Ireland) according to manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, DNA was extracted using a papain extraction reagent for 3 h at 65 °C. 28.7 µl were then transferred into 96-well plate. A standard curve was generated using 0, 100, 200, 375, 500, 1000, 2000 and 4000 ng/ml DNA concentrations. 71.3 µl of a 1:200 dilution of Quant-iT™ PicoGreen® reagent was added to each sample and the plate was read using a micro-plate reader (Varioskan Flash, Thermo Scientific, Ireland) with an excitation wavelength of 480 nm and an emission wavelength of 525 nm.

2.15. Statistical analysis

Data are expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Statistical analysis was performed using MINITAB® version 19 (Minitab Inc., USA). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for multiple comparisons and Tukey's post hoc test was used for pairwise comparisons when the group distributions were normal (Anderson-Darling normality test) and variances of populations were equal (Bonett's test and Levene's test). When either or both assumptions were violated, non-parametric analysis was conducted using Kruskal-Wallis test for multiple comparisons and Mann-Whitney test for pairwise comparisons. Results were considered statistically significant for $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Biophysical characterisation

All fucoidan concentrations exhibited significant lower ($p < 0.05$) negative charge than carrageenan and among the various fucoidan concentrations assessed, the 50 µg/ml and 100 µg/ml fucoidan concentrations exhibited the lowest ($p < 0.05$) negative charge (Fig. 2A). Among all groups, the 100 µg/ml, 250 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml fucoidan concentrations exhibited the lowest ($p < 0.05$) PDI (Fig. 2B). No statistically

significant ($p > 0.05$) differences were observed in hydrodynamic radius (Fig. 2C). The 250 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml fucoidan concentrations exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) % FVO among all groups (Fig. 2D).

All galactofucan concentrations exhibited significant lower ($p < 0.05$) negative charge than carrageenan and among the various galactofucan concentrations assessed, the 500 µg/ml galactofucan concentration exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) negative charge (Fig. 2E). Among all groups, the 250 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml galactofucan concentrations exhibited the lowest ($p < 0.05$) PDI (Fig. 2F). No statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) differences were observed in hydrodynamic radius (Fig. 2G) between the groups. The 50 µg/ml and 250 µg/ml galactofucan concentrations exhibited the highest ($p < 0.01$) % FVO among all groups (Fig. 2H).

All arabinogalactan concentrations exhibited significant lower ($p < 0.05$) negative charge than carrageenan and no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found among the assessed arabinogalactan concentrations (Fig. 2I). The 100 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml arabinogalactan concentrations exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) PDI (Fig. 2J). The 100 µg/ml, 250 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml arabinogalactan concentrations exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) hydrodynamic radius (Fig. 2K). All arabinogalactan concentrations exhibited significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher % FVO than carrageenan and among the various arabinogalactan concentrations assessed, the 100 µg/ml, 250 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml arabinogalactan concentrations exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) % FVO (Fig. 2L).

All ulvan concentrations exhibited significant lower ($p < 0.05$) negative charge than carrageenan and among the various ulvan concentrations assessed, the 500 µg/ml ulvan concentration exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) negative charge (Fig. 2M). The 250 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml ulvan concentrations exhibited the lowest ($p < 0.05$) PDI (Fig. 2N). The 25 µg/ml and 50 µg/ml ulvan concentrations exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) hydrodynamic radius among all groups (Fig. 2O). All ulvan concentrations exhibited significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher % FVO than carrageenan and among the various ulvan concentrations assessed, the 250 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml ulvan concentrations exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) % FVO (Fig. 2P).

3.2. Basic cellular function assessment

Cell morphology (Supplementary Fig. S1A) and viability (Supplementary Fig. S1B) were not affected as a function of carrageenan addition and fucoidan concentrations. With respect to cell number, at all timepoints carrageenan exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) proliferation; at day 4, all fucoidan concentrations had similar ($p > 0.05$) proliferation to each other and to - MMC group; at day 7, the 25 µg/ml and 50 µg/ml fucoidan concentrations showed higher ($p < 0.05$) proliferation in comparison to the other fucoidan concentrations and to - MMC group; and at day 10, only the 500 µg/ml fucoidan concentration had lower ($p < 0.05$) proliferation to the other fucoidan concentrations and to - MMC group (Supplementary Fig. S1C). At all timepoints carrageenan had lower ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity than the - MMC group and the 500 µg/ml fucoidan concentration at day 4 and day 7 and all fucoidan concentrations at day 10; at day 4 and day 7, all fucoidan concentrations, but the 500 µg/ml concentration, had lower ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity to - MMC group and among them, the 500 µg/ml fucoidan concentration had the highest ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity and at day 10, only the 500 µg/ml fucoidan concentration had higher ($p < 0.05$) metabolic activity than the - MMC group and the other fucoidan concentrations (Supplementary Fig. S1D).

Cell morphology (Supplementary Fig. S2A) and viability (Supplementary Fig. S2B) were not affected as a function of galactofucan concentrations. With respect to cell number, at all timepoints carrageenan exhibited the highest ($p < 0.001$) proliferation; at day 4, all galactofucan concentrations had similar ($p > 0.05$) proliferation to - MMC group and among them, the 500 µg/ml galactofucan concentration was significantly the lowest ($p < 0.05$); at day 7, the 50 µg/ml and 250 µg/ml

Fig. 2. Zeta potential analysis (A, E, I, M) showed that fucoidan, galactofucan, arabinogalactan and ulvan at all concentrations had significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower negative charge than carrageenan (CR). Fucoidan (B), galactofucan (F) and ulvan (N) exhibited significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower polydispersity index (PDI) than CR at their high concentrations, whilst arabinogalactan (J) exhibited significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower PDI than CR at low concentrations and at 250 µg/ml concentration. No significant ($p > 0.05$) differences were found in the hydrodynamic radius of fucoidan (C) and galactofucan (G) as a function of their concentrations and in comparison to CR, whilst the high concentrations of arabinogalactan (K) and the low concentrations and the 250 µg/ml concentration of ulvan (O) exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) hydrodynamic radius within their respective group and CR. Fucoidan (D) exhibited significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher % FVO than CR at the high (250 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml) concentrations, galactofucan (H) exhibited significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher % FVO than CR at 50 µg/ml and 250 µg/ml concentrations and arabinogalactan (L) and ulvan (P) had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher % FVO than CR at all concentrations. * indicates statistically significant difference to CR ($p < 0.05$). + indicates statistically significant difference among the tested polysaccharide concentrations ($p < 0.05$). N = 3.

galactofucan concentrations had higher ($p < 0.05$) proliferation than the - MMC group and the other galactofucan concentrations; and at day 10, the 500 µg/ml galactofucan concentration had the lowest ($p < 0.01$) proliferation and the 50 µg/ml and the 100 µg/ml galactofucan concentrations had higher ($p < 0.01$) proliferation than the - MMC group and the other galactofucan concentrations (Supplementary Fig. S2C). At all timepoints, carrageenan had lower ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity to - MMC group and to 500 µg/ml galactofucan concentration at day 4, to 25 µg/ml and 500 µg/ml galactofucan concentrations at day 7 and to all galactofucan concentrations at day 10; at day 4, the 500 µg/ml galactofucan concentration had similar ($p > 0.05$) metabolic activity to - MMC and all other galactofucan concentrations had lower ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity to - MMC; at day 7, all galactofucan concentrations had lower ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity to - MMC and among them, the 500 µg/ml galactofucan concentration had the highest ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity; and at day 10, the 25 µg/ml galactofucan concentration had similar ($p > 0.05$) metabolic activity to - MMC and among them, the 500 µg/ml galactofucan concentration had the highest ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity, even higher than the - MMC ($p < 0.01$) (Supplementary Fig. S2D).

Morphological analysis of hADSCs cultured with arabinogalactan revealed an abnormal morphology with progressive cell clustering and detachment over the timepoints (Supplementary Fig. S3A). Cell viability analysis showed the presence of dead cells at higher concentrations and cell detachment over the timepoints (Supplementary Fig. S3B). At all timepoint, carrageenan exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) cell proliferation; at day 4 and day 7, no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were observed between the arabinogalactan concentrations

and the - MMC group and within the arabinogalactan concentrations; and at day 10, all arabinogalactan concentrations had lower ($p < 0.05$) cell proliferation to the - MMC group (Supplementary Fig. S3C). At day 4, all arabinogalactan concentrations induced lower ($p < 0.05$) metabolic activity than the - MMC group and the 500 µg/ml arabinogalactan concentration exhibited lower ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity than the other arabinogalactan concentrations and the carrageenan group; at day 7, all arabinogalactan concentrations induced lower ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity than the - MMC group and the 25 µg/ml arabinogalactan concentration exhibited similar ($p > 0.05$) to carrageenan metabolic activity and the highest ($p < 0.05$) metabolic activity within the arabinogalactan groups; and at day 10, the carrageenan and the 50 µg/ml arabinogalactan concentration exhibited similar ($p > 0.05$) between them and the lowest ($p < 0.05$) metabolic activity among all groups, whilst the 500 µg/ml arabinogalactan concentration exhibited the highest ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity among all groups (Supplementary Fig. S3D). Arabinogalactan was excluded from any further analysis.

Cell morphology (Supplementary Fig. S4A) and viability (Supplementary Fig. S4B) were not affected as a function of ulvan concentrations. At day 4, carrageenan and all ulvan concentrations exhibited higher ($p < 0.01$) proliferation than the - MMC group and the 500 µg/ml ulvan concentration exhibited lower ($p < 0.05$) proliferation than the other ulvan concentrations; at day 7, carrageenan and all ulvan concentrations exhibited higher ($p < 0.05$) proliferation than the - MMC group and within the ulvan groups, the 100 µg/ml ulvan concentration exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) proliferation; and at day 10, carrageenan exhibited the highest ($p < 0.001$) proliferation and the 100 µg/ml ulvan concentration exhibited higher ($p < 0.05$) proliferation than

the other ulvan groups and the - MMC group (Supplementary Fig. S4C). At day 4, carrageenan and all ulvan concentrations induced lower ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity than the - MMC group and within the ulvan groups, the 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ulvan concentration exhibited the lowest ($p < 0.05$) metabolic activity; at day 7, carrageenan and all ulvan concentrations induced lower ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity than the - MMC group and within the ulvan groups, the 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ulvan concentrations exhibited the highest ($p < 0.05$) metabolic activity; and at day 10, carrageenan induced the lowest ($p < 0.01$) metabolic activity, all ulvan concentrations induced higher ($p < 0.05$) metabolic activity than carrageenan and among ulvan concentrations, the 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ulvan concentration exhibited the lowest ($p < 0.05$) metabolic activity (Supplementary Fig. S4D).

3.3. Deposited ECM analysis

SDS-PAGE (Fig. 3A) and corresponding densitometric analysis (Fig. 3B) made apparent that all timepoints carrageenan and all fucoidan concentrations induced higher ($p < 0.05$) collagen deposition than the - MMC group; between the carrageenan and the fucoidan groups, the 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ fucoidan concentration induced the lowest ($p < 0.05$) collagen deposition at all timepoints; and at day 10, the

500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ fucoidan concentration induced higher ($p < 0.01$) collagen deposition than the other fucoidan concentrations.

SDS-PAGE (Fig. 3C) and corresponding densitometric analysis (Fig. 3D) made apparent that all timepoints carrageenan and all galactofucan concentrations induced higher ($p < 0.05$) collagen deposition than the - MMC group; between the carrageenan and the galactofucan groups, the 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ galactofucan concentration induced the lowest ($p < 0.05$) collagen deposition at all timepoints; at day 7 and day 10, carrageenan induced higher ($p < 0.05$) collagen deposition than any galactofucan concentration.

SDS-PAGE (Fig. 3E) and corresponding densitometric analysis (Fig. 3F) made apparent that all timepoints carrageenan induced the highest ($p < 0.01$) collagen deposition than any other groups; the 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ulvan concentrations did not increase ($p > 0.05$) collagen deposition in comparison to the - MMC group at any timepoint; and at day 10, within the ulvan groups, the 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ulvan concentrations induced the highest ($p < 0.05$) collagen deposition.

Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S5A) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4A) made apparent that at day 4, the 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ fucoidan concentration induced the highest ($p < 0.05$) collagen type I deposition, at day 7, carrageenan induced the

Fig. 3. SDS-PAGE (A) and complementary densitometric analysis normalised to cell number (B) revealed that at all timepoints carrageenan (CR) and all fucoidan concentrations induced significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher collagen I deposition than the - MMC group. SDS-PAGE (C) and corresponding densitometric analysis normalised to cell number (D) made apparent that at all timepoints CR and all galactofucan concentrations induced significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher collagen deposition than the - MMC group. SDS-PAGE (E) and corresponding densitometric analysis normalised to cell number (F) made apparent that CR at all time points and only at day 10, the 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ulvan concentrations induced significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher collagen deposition than the - MMC group. * indicates statistically significant difference to - MMC ($p < 0.05$). + indicates statistically significant difference to CR ($p < 0.05$). # indicates statistically significant difference among the tested polysaccharide concentrations ($p < 0.05$). N = 3.

highest ($p < 0.05$) collagen type I deposition and at day 10, the 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ fucoidan concentration induced the highest ($p < 0.01$) collagen type I deposition. Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S5B) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4B) made apparent that at day 4 and day 7, all galactofucan concentrations induced lower ($p < 0.05$) collagen type I deposition than carrageenan and at day 10, the 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ galactofucan concentration induced higher ($p < 0.05$) collagen type I deposition than the - MMC group. Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S5C) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4C) made apparent that at day 4 and day 7, all ulvan concentrations induced lower ($p < 0.05$) collagen type I deposition than carrageenan and at day 10, the 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ulvan concentration induced similar ($p > 0.05$) collagen

type I deposition to carrageenan and higher ($p < 0.05$) than the - MMC group.

Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S6A) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4D) made apparent that neither carrageenan nor any of the fucoidan concentrations increased ($p > 0.05$) collagen type III deposition in comparison to the - MMC group. Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S6B) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4E) made apparent that carrageenan and all galactofucan groups induced similar ($p > 0.05$) collagen type III deposition at day 4 and day 10 and at day 7, the 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ galactofucan concentration induced the highest ($p < 0.05$) collagen type III deposition within the galactofucan groups. Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S6C) and complementary

Fig. 4. Relative fluorescent intensity analysis normalised to cell number revealed that in general, carrageenan (CR) and the high concentrations of fucoidan (A), galactofucan (B) and ulvan (C) deposited significantly ($p < 0.05$) more collagen I than the - MMC group. No significant ($p > 0.05$) differences in relative fluorescent intensity analysis normalised to cell number of collagen type III were detected between the crowded and - MMC groups (D, E, F). At day 10, CR, all concentrations of fucoidan (G), all concentrations of galactofucan (H) and all concentrations of ulvan but the 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (I) induces significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher collagen type V deposition than the - MMC group, as revealed by relative fluorescent intensity analysis normalised to cell number. No significant ($p > 0.05$) increases in relative fluorescent intensity analysis normalised to cell number of fibronectin were detected between the crowded and - MMC groups (J, K, L). * indicates statistically significant difference to - MMC ($p < 0.05$). + indicates statistically significant difference to CR ($p < 0.05$). # indicates statistically significant difference among the tested polysaccharide concentrations ($p < 0.05$). N = 3.

relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4F) made apparent that neither carrageenan nor any of the ulvan concentrations increased ($p > 0.05$) collagen type III deposition in comparison to the - MMC group.

Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S7A) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4G) made apparent that at day 4, the 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ fucoidan induced the highest ($p < 0.05$) collagen type V deposition; at day 7, carrageenan and the 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ fucoidan induced the highest ($p < 0.05$) collagen type V deposition and at day 10, carrageenan and all fucoidan concentrations induced higher ($p < 0.05$) collagen type V deposition than the - MMC group. Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S7B) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4H) made apparent that at day 4 there were no differences ($p > 0.05$) in collagen type V deposition between - MMC, carrageenan and any galactofucan concentration; at day 7, carrageenan and the 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ galactofucan concentration induced the highest ($p < 0.05$) collagen type V deposition; and at day 10, all galactofucan concentration induced higher ($p < 0.05$) collagen type V deposition and carrageenan induced the highest ($p < 0.001$) collagen type V deposition. Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S7C) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4I) made apparent that at day 10 carrageenan induced higher ($p < 0.05$) collagen type V deposition than any of the ulvan concentrations and at day 10, all ulvan concentrations, but the 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ulvan concentration, induced higher ($p < 0.05$) collagen type V deposition than the - MMC group.

Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S8A) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4J) made apparent that at day 4, day 7 and day 10, neither carrageenan nor any of the fucoidan concentrations increased ($p > 0.05$) fibronectin deposition and at all time points, 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ fucoidan concentrations induced higher ($p < 0.05$) fibronectin deposition than carrageenan. Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S8B) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4K) made apparent that at day 4, day 7 and day 10, neither carrageenan nor any of the galactofucan concentrations increased ($p > 0.05$) fibronectin deposition; at day 7, all galactofucan concentrations induced higher ($p < 0.05$) fibronectin deposition than the carrageenan group. Immunocytochemistry (Supplementary Fig. S8C) and complementary relative fluorescence intensity analysis (Fig. 4L) made apparent that at day 4, day 7 and day 10, neither carrageenan nor any of the ulvan concentrations increased ($p > 0.05$) fibronectin deposition; and at day 10, carrageenan induced the lowest ($p < 0.05$) fibronectin deposition.

3.4. Trilineage differentiation analysis

Phase contrast images (Supplementary Fig. S9A), alizarin red staining (Supplementary Fig. S10A) and corresponding absorbance quantification (Fig. 5A) of hADSCs cultured without MMC preconditioning and differentiated with osteogenic induction media with the various crowders (-/+ group) revealed that carrageenan, fucoidan and galactofucan deposited significantly ($p < 0.01$) higher amounts of calcium nodules in comparison to - MMC control (-/- group) and fucoidan and ulvan deposited significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower amounts of calcium nodules in comparison to carrageenan. hADSCs cultured with MMC pre-conditioning and differentiated without any crowders (+/- group) showed no significant ($p > 0.05$) differences between the groups. When cells were preconditioned with MMC and differentiated with crowders (+/+ group), carrageenan and galactofucan induced significantly ($p < 0.01$) higher calcium nodules deposition in comparison to fucoidan and ulvan.

Phase contrast images (Supplementary Fig. S9B), oil red O staining (Supplementary Fig. S10B) and corresponding absorbance quantification (Fig. 5B) of hADSCs cultured without MMC preconditioning and differentiated with adipogenic induction media with the various crowders (-/+ group) revealed that fucoidan and galactofucan significantly

($p < 0.01$) increased lipid droplets accumulation in comparison to - MMC (-/- group) and carrageenan and ulvan significantly ($p < 0.01$) decreased lipid droplets accumulation in comparison to - MMC, fucoidan and galactofucan groups. Negative control groups (no adipogenic induction) did not accumulate cytoplasmic lipid vacuoles. hADSCs cultured with MMC preconditioning and differentiated without any crowders (-/+ group) showed ulvan to significantly ($p < 0.05$) increase lipid droplets accumulation in comparison to carrageenan, fucoidan and galactofucan. When cells were preconditioned with MMC and differentiated with crowders (+/+ group) carrageenan and ulvan deposited significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower amount of lipid droplets in comparison to fucoidan and galactofucan.

Alcian blue staining (Supplementary Fig. S10C) and GAG quantification analysis (Fig. 5C) of hADSCs cultured without MMC preconditioning and differentiated with chondrogenic induction media with the various crowders (-/+ group) made apparent the presence of an abundant proteoglycan-rich ECM on the cell pellets in the presence of all crowders and all significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased GAG content when compared to - MMC control group (-/- group); no significant ($p > 0.05$) differences were observed between the crowders. hADSCs cultured with MMC preconditioning and differentiated without crowders (+/- group) did not reveal any significant ($p > 0.05$) differences between the groups. When cells were preconditioned with MMC and differentiated with crowders (+/+ group), fucoidan and galactofucan significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased GAG production in comparison to carrageenan and ulvan. Overall, carrageenan induced the highest osteogenic differentiation (+ 1039%) and the lowest adipogenic differentiation (- 39.4%). Carrageenan also induced the highest (+ 55.8) chondrogenic differentiation when hADSCs were not preconditioned with MMC (-/+ groups). Fucoidan (+ 174.4%) and galactofucan (+ 195.6%) induced the highest chondrogenic differentiation when present during the preconditioning and differentiation (+/+ groups) (Supplementary Table S2).

4. Discussion

Tissue engineering by self-assembly aspires to produce biomimetic modular structures by exploiting the intrinsic ability of permanently differentiated and stem cells to build tissues and organs [86,87]. The major limitation in the clinical translation of such strategies is the prolonged culture period required (during which cells lose their phenotype and therapeutic potential) to produce functional implantable devices with sufficient ECM. Although MMC has been shown consistently to enhance and accelerate ECM deposition, the ideal (with respect to enhanced and accelerated ECM deposition and controlled cell fate) crowding agent is still elusive. Herein, we ventured to assess the potential of seaweed-derived sulphated polysaccharides as MMC agents by assessing their effect on ECM deposition and lineage commitment of hADSCs. Carrageenan, a sulphated polysaccharide from red seaweeds, was used as a positive control MMC agent, as its efficiency as MMC agent has been well-established in the literature [46,53,55,88]. Carrageenan's questionable though association with colitis [75] imposes the need to identify alternative MMC agents. The rationale of choosing fucoidan, galactofucan, arabinogalactan and ulvan was based on the fact that they are all seaweed extracted sulphated polysaccharides. Biophysical (e.g. zeta potential, polydispersity index, hydrodynamic radius) and biological (e.g. cell morphology, viability, proliferation, metabolic activity, ECM synthesis and deposition and trilineage differentiation) analyses suggest that carrageenan, fucoidan and galactofucan can be utilised as MMC agents in hADSC cultures, especially for bone and cartilage engineering applications.

Starting with the biophysical analysis, the highest zeta potential of carrageenan can be attributed to its high sulphate content [89]. We also observed variations in zeta potential with changing the concentration of the tested polysaccharides, which is in agreement with previous publications [90]. All polysaccharides assessed were of high dispersity,

Fig. 5. Absorbance quantification of alizarin red staining revealed that carrageenan (CR), fucoidan and galactofucan only in the induction media (-/+) induced significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher amounts of calcium nodules in comparison to the non-crowded group (-/-) and among the +/+ groups, CR and galactofucan induced the highest ($p < 0.05$) calcium nodules deposition (A). Absorbance quantification of oil red O staining revealed that none of the tested polysaccharides had a notable effect in in vitro adipogenesis (B). GAG quantification analysis revealed that all crowders when only in the induction media (-/+) significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased GAG content in comparison to the -/- group, and among the +/+ groups, only fucoidan and galactofucan significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased GAG production (C). -/- indicates that hADSCs were preconditioned and differentiated without MMC. -/+ indicates that hADSCs were preconditioned without MMC and differentiated with MMC. +/- indicates that hADSCs were pre-conditioned with MMC and differentiated without MMC. +/+ indicates that hADSCs were preconditioned and differentiated with MMC. Preconditioned samples were compared only between the crowder groups. * indicates statistically significant difference to - MMC ($p < 0.05$). + indicates statistically significant difference to CR ($p < 0.05$). # indicates statistically significant difference among the tested polysaccharide concentrations ($p < 0.05$). N = 3.

which is expected, considering that seaweeds generate molecules of different chemistry, size and shape depending on the growth needs [75]. Further, it is worth noting that the biochemical and biophysical properties of seaweed polysaccharides strongly depend on their origin and the isolation and purification protocols used [91]. It is important to consider that polydispersity index, hydrodynamic radius and fraction volume occupancy should be calculated, assessed and compared at a given concentration optimal for the molecule studied. This is very important as high concentration of particles results in multi-scattering or in unpredictable agglomeration, whilst too dilute samples may not generate enough light to analyse [92,93]. So, at concentration of 50 µg/ml (concentration of carrageenan, positive control), fucoidan showed similar polydispersity index, hydrodynamic radius and fraction volume occupancy to carrageenan, galactofucan showed similar polydispersity index and hydrodynamic radius, but higher fraction volume occupancy than carrageenan, arabinogalactan showed lower polydispersity index, similar hydrodynamic radius and higher fraction volume occupancy than carrageenan and ulvan showed lower polydispersity index, higher hydrodynamic radius and similar fraction volume occupancy than carrageenan. As with zeta potential, these differences can be attributed to the origin and processing of the polysaccharides studied herein, as well as to their molecular weight [94]. With respect to % FVO, our calculations (> 500%) are well above values reported for other crowders (e.g. 5.2% for dextran sulphate 500 kDa [95], 18% for a cocktail of Ficoll™ 70 kDa and Ficoll™ 400 kDa [84] and 18% for polyvinylpyrrolidone 40 kDa and 54% for polyvinylpyrrolidone 360 kDa [50]). The % FVO is calculated from the molecular weight and the hydrodynamic radius, based on the assumption that the molecule in question is spherical. This high value of % FVO may be due to the fact that all the polysaccharides utilised are native grade with high estimated molecular weight. In addition, the sulphated polysaccharides in solution might have a non-spherical shape upon solvation, compromising the exact determination of the hydrodynamic radius during DLS measurements. For these reasons, these calculations should be treated with caution.

Cell response to the crowders showed that carrageenan, fucoidan, galactofucan and ulvan did not affect or only partially increased cell proliferation over the assessed timepoints. Previous studies have shown fucoidan to increase proliferation of human umbilical cord endothelial cells and skin fibroblasts [73,96,97], galactofucan to not negatively affect proliferation of human dermal fibroblasts [98] and rhamnose-rich polysaccharides, such as ulvan, to stimulate proliferation of human dermal fibroblasts [99]. Although we did not explore the exact mechanism through which the polysaccharides enhance cell proliferation, previous studies have shown fucoidan to enhance cell proliferation through heparin-like growth factor binding, protection and promotion [100].

Analysis of cell metabolic activity using alamarBlue® assay showed a decrease in cell metabolic activity when cells were cultured with carrageenan, fucoidan, galactofucan and ulvan. However, one should consider that the results were expressed as a percentage of alamarBlue® reduction and normalised to the cell number. Further, in cells with regular growth, the percentage of alamarBlue® reduced increases with time reaching a plateau at specific timepoints (usually 3–4 h) [101]. In our case, the groups treated with MMC may have reached the plateau earlier and the reduction in metabolic activity may be a mathematical artefact. After all, previous studies with carrageenan [46], fucoidan [102], galactofucan [103] and ulvan [104] did not reveal any cell toxicity. Arabinogalactan, on the other hand, resulted in abnormal cell morphology, detachment and apoptosis and was excluded from further analysis. This detachment may be attributed to buoyancy; considering that MMC significantly increases ECM deposition, the buoyancy of the cell-ECM layer is a lot stronger than the attachment forces between the tissue culture plastic and the cell-ECM layer, resulting in cell-ECM layer detachment. Cell detachment is associated with anoikis (detachment-induced apoptosis) [105–108] which further enhances our theory. We believe that this is a more plausible scenario, as opposed to toxicity,

considering that arabinogalactan-coated polyurethane scaffolds have been successfully used before for blood vessel reconstruction [109].

SDS-PAGE and ICC analyses revealed typical hADSC secretome. Indeed, previous studies have shown hADSCs to produce various ECM molecules (e.g. collagen type I [110], collagen type III [2], collagen type V [111], fibronectin [112]), all essential for physiological tissue development, healing and function. Indeed, collagen type I is the most abundant ECM molecule and plays a crucial role in the structural and biomechanical integrity of tissues and organs [113]. Collagen type III is a regulator of collagen I fibrillogenesis and modulates fibril diameter [114]. Collagen type V plays a critical role in collagen fibrillogenesis and also influences fibril diameter [115]. Fibronectin forms a fibril network that serves as a template for collagen fibril assembly into the ECM [116]. Further, all molecules assessed herein acted as macromolecular crowders; at low concentrations, they were rather ineffective in ECM deposition; as the concentration was increased, they more effectively excluded volume resulting in enhanced and accelerated ECM deposition; and after a certain concentration, a plateau was reached, which resulted in no further increase in ECM deposition. The observed increase in ECM deposition is in agreement with previous publications. For example, carrageenan has been comprehensively shown to enhance and accelerate ECM deposition in numerous cell types [53,55,88,117]. Fucoidan, isolated from *Ascophyllum nodosum* seaweeds, has been shown to reduce procollagen I excretion rate into the culture media and increase collagen type I in the cell layer of vascular smooth cells [118]. Galactofucan fraction with low molecular weight (< 10 kDa) has been reported to stimulate collagen I secretion, potentially play a role in correcting deficient wound healing [98] and accelerate angiogenesis and collagen deposition, resulting in enhanced re-epithelialization in a *in vivo* wound healing model [119]. Rhamnose-rich oligo- and polysaccharides have also been shown to stimulate collagen biosynthesis [99]. Further, although previous studies have supported that % FVO is key modulator of enhanced and accelerated ECM deposition [47,50,95], this was not confirmed herein. For example, although most crowders exhibited a lot higher % FVO than carrageenan, they did not appear to induce substantially more ECM deposition than carrageenan. This observation fits with our previous theory that enhanced and accelerated ECM deposition is dependent on negative charge and polydispersity [46,53].

Considering that fucoidan, galactofucan and ulvan did not substantially enhance and accelerate ECM deposition in hADSC cultures in comparison to carrageenan, we selected their respective minimum effective concentrations (50 µg/ml fucoidan, 50 µg/ml galactofucan and 250 µg/ml ulvan respectively) and we ventured to assess their influence on stem cell fate in correlation to 50 µg/ml carrageenan (hADSCs were cultured in the absence or presence of each crowder and were subsequently differentiated towards osteogenic, adipogenic and chondrogenic lineage, again, in the absence or presence of each crowder). Osteogenesis was significantly enhanced in the presence of crowders, which is in agreement with previous studies. Specifically, carrageenan has been shown to increase mineralisation and osteopontin expression in hBMSC cultures [54,55]. Fucoidan has been reported to increase alkaline phosphatase activity and the expression of osteogenesis-specific marker genes, including alkaline phosphatase, osteopontin, runt-related transcription factor 2 and osteocalcin in hADSC cultures [120] and to induce osteoblast differentiation of human alveolar BMSCs through BMP2-Smad 1/5/8 signalling by activating ERK and JNK [97]. Photo-crosslinked ulvan scaffolds have been shown to induce and support enzyme-mediated formation of apatite minerals, even in the absence of osteogenic growth factors [121]. Carrageenan and ulvan appeared to inhibit adipogenesis, which again is in agreement with previous observations. Carrageenan has been shown to inhibit insulin signalling, which is a potent adipogenic hormone [70]. Low molecular weights fractions of ulvan have been demonstrated to lower the levels of serum total cholesterol and low density lipoprotein cholesterol, when fed to rats on a hypercholesterolemic diet for 21 days [122].

Fucoidan and galactofucan appeared to increase adipogenic differentiation. This may be a mathematical artefact, since absorbance values were normalised to DNA quantity and the two crowders led to partial cell detachment due to long culture period. After all, fucoidan has been shown to inhibit adipocyte differentiation, as evidenced by decreased lipid accumulation, downregulation of adipocyte markers and reduction in the expression of adipogenic transcription factors α (C/EBP α), γ (PPAR γ) and AP2, all crucial in adipocyte development [68,123]. Regarding chondrogenic differentiation, it was enhanced in the presence of the crowders, in agreement with previous publications. For example, fucoidan from *Undaria Pinnatifida* has been shown to induce type II collagen expression via the p38 and AKT pathways and COX-2 expression via the p38, ERK and AKT pathways in rabbit articular chondrocytes [124]. Over-sulphated marine polysaccharides have also been shown to increase chondrogenic differentiation of hADSCs by upregulating the phosphorylation of extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1–2 and affecting the mitogen activated protein kinase signalling activity [125]. An alginate-fucoidan composite hydrogel has also been shown to augment the chondrogenic differentiation of hBMSCs [82]. Carrageenan has also been shown to enhance chondrogenesis in hBMSC cultures [54,55].

5. Conclusion

Contemporary tissue engineering requires ways to enhance and accelerate extracellular matrix deposition, whilst controlling cell function, to develop therapies of both clinical and commercial value. Although macromolecular crowding has been shown enhance and accelerate extracellular matrix deposition and to control cell fate in vitro, the optimal macromolecular crowder has yet to be identified. Herein, we assessed the potential of sulphated seaweed in origin polysaccharides as macromolecular crowding agents. Data obtained demonstrate the potential of carrageenan, fucoidan and galactofucan as macromolecular crowders in human adipose derived stem cell cultures, especially for bone and cartilage engineering applications.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Author contribution

Andrea De Pieri and Dimitrios I. Zeugolis designed the study and edited and wrote the manuscript. Andrea De Pieri, Shubhasmin Rana and Stefanie Korntner carried out experiments. Andrea De Pieri analysed the data. All authors have approved the manuscript.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.07.087>.

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